

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Ismatullayeva N.R.

PLANNING FOR A NATIONAL MALAY LANGUAGE

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUN

